

On the successful pelletization of a fragile mesoporous material and its mechanical stability mechanism

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ABSTRACT

Mechanical stability is a crucial property for the industrial implementation of heterogeneous catalysts and adsorbents. Both particle size and shape need to be investigated for each application where, typically, a compromise between mass transfer and pressure drop needs to be understood. In this study, we investigate the mechanical stability of a fragile mesostructured cellular foam material, formed of 3D aluminosilicate struts and porous cages, that are connected through windows. Successful pelletization was found at ca. 20 MPa, where the structural and textural properties are either unaltered or minimally modified. This condition is satisfactory for the final application of the pelletized material, though a lower-limit pressure could still be optimized. The use of higher pelletization pressures was observed to increase disorder in the systems. The structure contracts, the cage's size decreases markedly leading to more disordered wormhole-like pores. The decrease in cage/pore size seems to compensate for the structural densification, resulting in relatively constant BET areas. The pore volume's decrease is in agreement with the smaller cage sizes and densification. The damage and the mechanism causing this damage differ from that observed in conventional mesoporous materials. Besides the successful pelletization conditions and identification of damage mechanism, it is also noteworthy to highlight that values for BET area can be misleading when assessing mechanical stability; at high pressures, the BET areas remain fairly constant despite significant changes in pore size and structure are observed.

1. Introduction

Heterogeneous catalysts and adsorbents are rarely used as loose powders. Material shaping is commonly a required step for industrial application [1,2]. In general, the chosen size/shape, of such forms, is a compromise between tailoring mass transfer, to minimize diffusion limitations (with small particles) and pressure drop (large particles). Other important factors determining size/shape are the required fluid-dynamic regime, mechanical strength, heat transfer and abrasion resistance to withstand transportation, filling and use within the desired reactor or adsorption column [1,3,4].

Academic studies on heterogeneous catalysts hardly consider shaping, with the exception of structured catalysts [5,6], however, the size of catalyst particles is greatly studied. This is due to the fact that most of the reported studies are based on solid catalysts using a well-defined particle size distribution to avoid mass-transfer limitations.

After synthesis, powdered materials are typically pelletized, crushed and sieved to obtain suitable particle size distributions. Particle size is important particularly when considering pressure drop and mass-transfer diffusional limitations [7]. In catalyst characterisation studies, such as operando transmission FTIR, the pelletization pressure can also be critical and needs to be considered carefully [8]. All the above means that the mechanical strength of a catalytic material, or adsorbent, needs to be investigated; as how the process of pelletization affects the structure, porosity, and catalytic/adsorption behavior.

The mechanical strength of well-known powdery mesoporous materials has been reported, including MCM-41 [9–13], MCM-48 [9,11,13], SBA-15 [10,11,13–15], KIT-1 [11], FSM-16 [11,13], HMS [11,13], PHTS [13], SBA-1 [16], SBA-3 [10], FDU-12 [17], SBA-16 [17], COK-12 [18]. Occasionally, mesoporous thin films have been studied [19]. For powdery mesoporous materials, both structural and textural damage have been observed upon the application of external pressure. A

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Fig. 1. Textural and structural features of the non-pelletized MSU: a) SAXS (the high q -value reflection denoted as 'silica' represents the short-range order of the network), b) TEM, c) nitrogen sorption isotherm, and d) BJH pore size distributions indicating the cage and window size distributions.

maximum pressure that a material can withstand has been defined as the pressure at which either pore volume or the most intense diffraction band decreases by 10 % [11] or 50 % [13].

In this work, we have probed the mechanical stability of a mesoporous material denoted as MSU-F [20] (originally reported as mesostructured cellular foam (MCF) materials [21,22]). It consists of a three-dimensional ultra-large-pore mesoporous material, where spherical mesopores (denoted as cages) are connected through windows. MSU does not have a typical channelled structure with walls but it is a 3D aluminosilicate spherical strut-like structure, also denoted "cells" with porous interconnected cages. In this regard, it can be considered structurally fragile, or more fragile than the typical MCM-41 or SBA-15 materials. A suitable pelletization pressure that minimizes the damage was identified and the mechanical stability phenomena at higher pressures were rationalised.

2. Experimental methods

2.1. Materials

The mesoporous aluminosilicate was purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Al-MSU-F, code 643629) and denoted as MSU in the manuscript. It consists of a very-fine powdery solid material.

2.2. Pelletization experiments

The pelletization experiments were carried out in a Carver press, with an accuracy of one decimal in the employed force range. The fresh MSU was loaded in a 13-mm-diameter die and pressed at ca. 22 MPa (0.3 Ton), 133 MPa (1.8 Ton), and 480 MPa (6.5 Ton) for about 5 min. For the sake of clarity, fresh MSU was employed for each test. In the case of 22 MPa, a low-pressure press was employed ranging from 0 to 1 Ton. This type of mechanical test is often denoted as a uniaxial compression test [10,12]. The materials were then crushed and sieved into the 212–425 μm fraction for further characterization. This fraction is typical for a reaction of industrial interest [23–31]. Note that differences may arise from one press to another press due to differences in the calibration of the pressure gauge and accuracy in reading the gauge reading panel itself. The studied pressures are based on the accuracy of the press, with one decimal in the force. The resulting pressures were subsequently calculated. Obtaining pressures as round numbers can be difficult. For instance, setting the pressure at 20 MPa would require 0.271 Ton, and this is unachievable with our equipment (one decimal accuracy).

Fig. 2. SAXS patterns of the studied mesoporous MSU materials (black lines), alongside Monte Carlo fits (red circles) and the resultant form-free size distribution histograms (purple bars). The high q -value reflection denoted as 'silica' represents the short-range order of the silica network. Samples: a) MSU, b) MSU22, c) MSU133 and d) MSU480.

2.3. Characterization

2.3.1. Elemental analysis

The elemental composition was determined by quantification of the Si and Al concentrations in solution by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) in a Thermo Scientific™ iCAP PRO ICP-Optical Emission Spectrometer. Before analysis, ca. 40 mg of the sample was dissolved using a concentrated hydrofluoric and nitric acid solution [32].

2.3.2. Gas adsorption analyses

Nitrogen adsorption isotherms were measured on a TriStar II Plus analyzer (Micromeritics). All samples were degassed at 90 °C for 2 h followed by 300 °C for 16 h prior to the analysis. The specific surface areas were determined following the recommendations described elsewhere and denoted as 'BET area' [33]. The pore volume was determined at $P/P_0 = 0.98$ in the desorption branch [34]. The pore size distributions were derived from the BJH model. The authors are aware of the limitations of this model [35], so the values have been used for relative comparison among the materials. Available NLDFT models [36] did not provide meaningful results.

2.3.3. Small-angle X-ray scattering

Small-angle X-ray scattering data was collected on all samples using an SAXSpoint 2.0 instrument from Anton Paar. Scattering data was collected on an Eiger 1M detector (Dectris, Switzerland) positioned 113 and 552 mm from the sample, using a microfocused, monochromatized X-ray source $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm). The samples were held in the beam between two pieces of Scotch Magic tape, and the resulting data was

processed using the DAWN software package, using standardized data correction procedures [37,38]. The corrected data were fit using McSAS3, based on Monte Carlo simulations, to obtain form-free size distributions, using a hard sphere model [39].

2.3.4. Transmission electron microscopy

High-Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM) images were acquired with a Gatan Orius™ SC200 CCD camera in a JEOL JEM 3000 F microscope ($C_s = 0.6$ mm) operated at 300 kV. The microscope is equipped with an Oxford Instruments Xplore™ detector and an AZtec™ microanalysis suite for XEDS analysis. The equipment is located at the Centro Nacional de Microscopía Electrónica, Madrid.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Properties of the non-pelletized MSU

The starting material is a mesoporous aluminosilicate with a molar Si/Al of ca. 47 as determined by elemental analysis (Table S1). The SAXS pattern for MSU (Fig. 1a) is comprised of three broad reflections (i.e., bumps), observed at ca. 0.30, 0.52 and 0.77 nm^{-1} . These bumps are thought to stem from the differences in electron density observed between the aluminosilicate scaffold and the pores/voids found within the material that are commonly referred altogether to as cells [21,22]. A recent study, on a comparable mesocellular silica foam structure, reported that such contributions can occur due to the co-presence of a distorted hexagonal lattice [40], and it is thought that such contributions could also be present here. Monte Carlo fits of the SAXS data (Fig. 2a) show that there is a relatively narrow population with a

Table 1Textural properties derived from N₂ physisorption at −196 °C. For clarity, the applied mechanical pressure in the pelletization has been indicated.

Material	Pressure ^(a) (MPa)	a ₀ ^(b) (nm)	S _{BET} ^(c,d,e) (m ² /g)	C ^(e) (−)	V _T ^(c) (cm ³ /g)	V _{micro} ^(c) (cm ³ /g)	Φ _{BH} ^(c,f) (nm)	Φ _{BH} ^(c,g) (nm)
MSU	None	24.538	561 ± 1	103	1.971	0.016	20.6	13.7
MSU22	22 (0.3)	24.341	549 ± 1	101	1.927	0.018	20.6	12.8
MSU133	133 (1.8)	24.099	548 ± 1	114	1.006	0.020	13.4	6.7
MSU480	480 (6.5)	23.788	539 ± 1	104	1.040	0.019	13.1	6.1

^a Values in parentheses are the applied force in Tons. The studied pressures are based on the accuracy of the press with one decimal in the force.^b a₀ is the obtained lattice parameter (pore center to center distance) obtained from SAXS, calculated using the following equation, where q is the scattering vector:

$$a_0 = \frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}q}$$

^c The value corresponds to the average between two measurements giving similar results. The isotherms and pore size distributions can be found in Figs. 3 and 4.^d The BET model was applied in all cases in the P/P₀ region 0.05–0.20 and complying with the Rouquerol conditions.^e The given error corresponds to that coming from the linearization.^f This corresponds to the cage's diameter.^g This corresponds to the window's diameter.

diameter of ca. 22 nm and a secondary, much broader population at ca. 9 nm in diameter. These observed populations are thought to be representative of the cage and window structures, respectively, and are discussed in further detail alongside TEM and physisorption data. TEM data reveal the presence of cells/cages formed by disordered aluminosilicate

struts (Fig. 1b). From the image, the size of the cells/cages appears to be regular as spherical/spheroidal shapes. Later, additional TEM pictures will be discussed showing the same pattern. The porosity was evaluated by N₂ physisorption at its boiling temperature, showing a type IV isotherm with H1 hysteresis (Fig. 1c). This is characteristic of solids with

Fig. 3. Nitrogen sorption isotherms of the mesoporous MSU materials: a) MSU, b) MSU22, c) MSU133, and d) MSU480. A duplicate for each material is included, denoted with (d) in the sample's name.

Fig. 4. BJH pore size distributions derived from N_2 physisorption data of the mesoporous MSU materials: a) MSU, b) MSU22, c) MSU133, and d) MSU480. A duplicate for each material is included, denoted with (d) in the sample's name.

a narrow range of uniform mesopores, with good connectivity [33,41]. The isotherm does not level off at high P/P_0 , indicating that there is additional unfilled macroporosity [33,42]. The pore size distributions provide information of the cage's size (adsorption branch) and window's size (desorption), Fig. 1d [21,22]. Both distributions are narrow and centered at ca. 21 and 14 nm (Table 1), respectively. The window's size appears to be bimodal with a smaller contribution at around 10 nm. This is slightly different from recent studies on the same material, which displayed a monomodal distribution [31,42]. This can be related to differences between synthesis batches, or differences in the data resolution, or both effects. A BET area of $561 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and the pore volume of $1.971 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ (Table 1), are in agreement with literature [31,42]. The porosity shows a small contribution of microporosity as a shoulder towards low pores (Fig. 1d), where the t -plot analysis reveals $0.016 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ of microporosity (Table 1).

The above characterization indicates that the structure contains uniform ink-bottle-type pores in which large cages are interconnected by windows of smaller sizes. The solid structure is formed by thin disordered aluminosilicate struts.

3.2. Pelletized materials

The powdery MSU was subjected to various unilateral pressures and the sieved materials were characterized. The study is divided in two sections. Firstly, the successful pelletization pressure where the properties were unaltered, or minimally altered, will be discussed. Then, higher pressures were studied and their effect on structure and porosity will be discussed, including its degradation mechanism.

3.2.1. Successful pelletization conditions

Mechanically-stable pellets were formed upon applying a pressure of ca. 20 MPa, which could be crushed and sieved. The resulting material (MSU22) was characterized, showing very similar features to the powdery MSU. The SAXS pattern, which shows the three bumps, is comparable to that for the native MSU (cf. Fig. 2b and a). Monte Carlo fits of the data, again, show two main populations, the cages with an average diameter ca. 22 nm and the windows with an average diameter ca. 9 nm (Fig. 2b), in strong alignment with observations from the powdery MSU sample (Fig. 2a). Nitrogen isotherm remains the same shape (cf. Fig. 3b–a) as well as the pore size distribution (cf. Fig. 4b–a). For the sake of reproducibility, repeat measurements were performed (Fig. 3) and pore size distributions calculated (Fig. 4), showing good

Fig. 5. TEM images for (a) MSU, (b) MSU22, (c) MSU133, and (d) MSU480.

reproducibility. The BET area and total pore volume for MSU22 only slightly decreased by ca. 2 % (Table 1). TEM images show comparable structures (cf. Fig. 5b–a), where the cell/cage’s sizes are uniform in size, i.e., relatively monodispersed spheres/spheroids. This is in agreement with the narrow adsorption pore size distributions (Fig. 4a/b) and SAXS fits (Fig. 2a/b) for MSU and MSU22. Note that from TEM data, we are

unable to visualize clearly the inner windows connecting cages, but only the outer windows.

Relevant parameters are represented as a function of the pelletization pressure in Fig. 6 (i.e., lattice parameter, cage and window sizes). It shows that these parameters are not altered, or minimally, for MSU22. This graph is further discussed in the next section.

Fig. 6. Representation of the lattice (a_0), cage ($\Phi_{\text{BJH}}^{\text{ADS}}$) and window ($\Phi_{\text{BJH}}^{\text{DES}}$) diameters as a function of the applied pressure. Raw data are given in Table 1. The lines are meant to guide the eye. Silica strut size = lattice – cage size = $a_0 - \Phi_{\text{BJH}}^{\text{ADS}}$.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the SAXS patterns.

In summary, the good structural preservation along with the minimal lowering of both BET area and pore volume (ca. 2 % both), are quite satisfactory results for the final application of the pelletized material. Additional optimization can be studied for pressures below 20 MPa to identify the lower limit to achieve stable pellets. This is an aspect that should be further studied in future work.

3.2.2. Higher-pressure pelletization

Additional pelletization experiments were carried out at ca. 133 and 480 MPa. The SAXS patterns of these materials are more diffuse than those obtained from MSU and MSU22 (Figs. 2 and 7). The observed bumps are less prominent/well-defined, indicating increased polydispersity within the structure [18]. It is also observed that the first maximum (Fig. 7, alpha) is shifted towards higher q -values, i.e., a decrease in the lattice/cell size (Table 1) [40]. Considering the SAXS patterns reported here, and previous reports in the literature, the structures observed are commonly referred to as wormhole structures, i.e., a disordered hexagonal-like arrangement of channels [18,43–45]. The Monte Carlo fits for the SAXS data show the signal from the cages is suppressed and is somewhat lost towards smaller sizes in the broad

distribution observed from the windows (Fig. 2c/d). The isotherms for MSU133 and MSU480 (Fig. 3c–d) change into a type IV and hysteresis H2(b), indicating pore blocking but with a broad distribution. The tensile strength effect (TSE) is visible [46,47] but the portion of blocked pores is low, from the shape of the isotherm [13].

In agreement with the SAXS observations, the pore size distributions show that the cage's size becomes much broader and smaller (Fig. 4c–d) than MSU/MSU22 (Fig. 4a–b). The window's size becomes smaller as well. All this means that the pore network has shrunk due to high-pressure pelletization. These effects can be observed in the TEM data as well. The more regular cell/cage sizes in MSU and MSU22 (Fig. 5a–b) are absent in MSU133 and MSU480 (Fig. 5c–d). From the TEM images, the pore sizes are smaller, resembling a wormhole structure where the (more) regular cells/cages are no longer visible or are less obvious to see.

The lattice parameter remains relatively constant for all materials with a slight decrease (Table 1), whereas cage's and window's size decrease for MSU133 and MSU480. This could indicate that, for these materials, the aluminosilicate struts become thicker (strut size = lattice – cage size). This can be seen in Fig. 6, and it is interpreted as a densification of the material. Note that the employed cage sizes for calculations of the strut size are at the maximum of the distribution. However, it is important to note that for MSU133 and MSU480, the distributions are broad and representing such parameters with a single value does not necessarily fully describe the material (Fig. 4c–d). Moreover, bear in mind that the BJH model has some limitations to assess the pore size with accuracy [35]. Therefore, based on all the above, the concept of the 'strut thickness' is here intended to give an idea that the struts became thicker, and a densification occurs at high pressure, but the thickness is certainly broad in size for these materials, particularly for MSU133 and MSU480.

In summary, at high pressures the lattice parameter remains fairly constant, cage's and window's size decrease and densification has been here proven via a thicker strut size.

To help the reader understand the structural changes easier, Fig. 8 shows a scheme illustrating the change upon high pressure. A more ordered MSU structure (left) changes into a wormhole disordered structure (right). The latter displaying thicker strut size, smaller pores and broad pore size distribution. Note that the structural dimensions should be interpreted in semi-quantitative terms.

3.2.3. Relative changes of textural parameters

The relative changes of total pore volume and BET area are given in Fig. 9. MSU22 displays very small changes with respect to the pristine MSU, a 2 % change in both parameters. The trend line for the total pore volume is in agreement with the observed changes in the pore size distributions; smaller pore sizes upon pelletization contribute less to the total pore volume. Both MSU133 and MSU480 display the same smaller cage size distributions (Fig. 4c–d) and their total pore volumes are comparable and smaller than that for MSU. Densification as shown earlier or bulk density's increase, i.e., more mass per volume, also contributes here as there is more mass per volume and the total pore volume is defined as cm^3/g . The trend line for the BET area was nearly constant and unexpected. It was unexpected that the BET area for the MSU133 and MSU480 were very similar to the MSU (only 2 and 4 % lower). From the literature, the BET area for pelletized mesoporous materials typically decreases, e.g. Refs. [11,12,15,18], but here it remains fairly constant. If only the BET area is considered, this may let the reader think that nothing changes in the material. However, it seems that there are opposing effects in the BET area that counteract each other. On the one hand, the bulk density of the material increases upon pelletization, so the mass per volume increases; this is detrimental for the BET area as it is defined as m^2/g . In other words, 1 g of material contains less porosity. This has been observed during the mechanical tests of MCM-41, SBA-15 or COK-12 where some channels collapse and the rest remains open with the same pore size [11,12,15,18]. On the

Fig. 8. Left) Schematic cross section of the strut-like caged structure exhibited by MSU and MSU22. The grey-shaded areas represent the aluminosilicate framework struts. The volume within the inorganic “cells” is the cage which are interconnected through windows. This scheme was reproduced from Schmidt-Winkel et al. [22]. Right) Wormhole structure upon high-pressure pelletization showing thicker struts, smaller pores and the pore distribution becomes broader, for MSU133 and MSU480. By similitude, the scheme was adapted from that observed in L_3 worm-like sponge phase in microemulsions [48]. The dimensions of these structures should be interpreted in semi-quantitative terms.

Fig. 9. Relative change of total pore volume (a) and BET area (b) as a function of the applied pressure.

other hand, here the pores become smaller and there may be more pores per volume; having a high proportion of smaller pores is known to contribute more to the BET area [41,49–51]. It seems that this effect (a high density of smaller pores) is compensating for the densification (more mass per volume), resulting in comparable BET areas.

Note that the C value of the BET model, which indicates the interaction between N_2 and the surface, remains constant for all materials (Table 1). This parameter, if it varies too much, can have an effect on the cross-sectional value of N_2 due to the orientation during the adsorption, and influence the BET values. However, this issue is not present here. The constant C values also indicate that the nature of the surface (hydroxylation degree) is comparable among the materials [35].

Finally, the microporosity remains fairly constant for all the materials (Table 1), so this parameter is not affected by the mechanical tests.

3.2.4. Mechanistic insights

Mechanistically, the observed changes in the MSU are different from materials such as MCM-41 [9–13] or SBA-15 [10,11,13–15]. In the latter cases, the lattice parameter obtained from SAXS remains constant, though secondary reflections are often lost, alongside an observed decrease in intensity, upon applying pressure. The physisorption pore size distributions, for those conventional mesoporous materials, also remain at the same position with decreased intensity upon mechanical pressure. All this indicates that some pores/channels are lost, with pores collapsing and the remaining porosity/order stemming from the non-collapsed channels/walls. Hence, the resulting material is not homogenous and contains domains of closed/collapsed channels, as well as open ones. For MSU, on the contrary, the structural and textural features change upon high-pressure pelletization; SAXS ordering, pore size and pore shape. Mechanistically, the whole structure is compressed isotropically (i.e., in all directions), most likely due to a higher flexibility of MSU than conventional mesoporous materials, resulting in a wormhole structure with smaller pores, thicker strut size and broad pore size distribution, as illustrated in Fig. 8.

4. Conclusions

The mechanical stability of a fragile mesostructured cellular foam material has been investigated. The structure is formed by 3D aluminosilicate nano-scale struts forming mesoporous cages that are connected by windows. Successful pelletization, i.e., by forming stable pellets that can be crushed and sieved, is achieved at ca. 20 MPa. The structural properties, as determined by SAXS and TEM are preserved, and the textural properties are minimally altered. Therefore, this mechanical pressure is satisfactory for final application of the pelletized

material. Yet, a lower-limit pressure to achieve stable pellets can still be optimized.

Application of higher pressures (i.e., 133 and 480 MPa) leads to severe damage with an evident loss of structural ordering, rendering structures with a more pronounced wormhole structure. This can be caused by smaller cell/cage's sizes, larger polydispersity, or both; both effects are observed experimentally by gas adsorption, Monte Carlo fits and TEM. The lower pore volume for those materials is in agreement with the smaller cage's size and densification (not measured directly but as larger strut thickness). The BET areas remain fairly constant, and this unexpected result is interpreted by a compensation of phenomena taking place during the high-pressure pelletizations; densification versus formation of smaller pores. Note that the BET area itself can be a misleading parameter when assessing the mechanical stability; various parameters should be considered in a comprehensive way. The mechanism of mechanical degradation for this material is different from conventional mesoporous materials. Here the structure is compressed isotropically where all the pores shrink, and the structure is distorted.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Silvia Morales-de-laRosa: Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Glen J. Smales:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Joaquín Martínez-Triguero:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Ignacio Melián-Cabrera:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2024.113322>.

References

- [1] F. Schüth, M. Hesse, Catalyst forming, in: J.G. Ertl, H. Knözinger, F. Schüth, J. Weitkamp (Eds.), *Handbook of Heterogeneous Catalysis*, vol. 1, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH, Weinheim, 2008, pp. 676–699.
- [2] I. Melián-Cabrera, Catalytic Materials: concepts to understand the pathway to implementation, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 60 (2021) 18545–18559, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.1c02681>.
- [3] T. Shoinkhorova, A. Dikhtiarenko, A. Ramirez, A.D. Chowdhury, M. Caglayan, J. Vittenet, A. Bendjeriou-Sedjerari, O.S. Ali, I. Morales-Osorio, W. Xu, W. Xu, J. Gascon, Shaping of ZSM-5-based catalysts via spray drying: effect on methanol-to-olefins performance, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 11 (2019) 44133–44143, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.9b14082>.
- [4] A.M. Alkadhem, H.O. Mohamed, S.R. Kulkarni, T. Hoffmann, D. Zapater, V. E. Musteata, E. Tsotsas, P. Castaño, Shaping technical catalyst particles in a bottom-spray fluidized bed, *Powder Technol.* 438 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2024.119602>.
- [5] F. Kapteijn, J.A. Moulijn, Structured catalysts and reactors – perspectives for demanding applications, *Catal. Today* 383 (2022) 5–14, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2020.09.026>.
- [6] G. Zhao, J.A. Moulijn, F. Kapteijn, F.M. Dautzenberg, B. Xu, Y. Lu, Monolithic fiber/foam-structured catalysts: beyond honeycombs and micro-channels, *Catal. Rev. - Sci. Eng.* (2023) 1–81, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01614940.2023.2240661>.
- [7] J. Pérez-Ramírez, R.J. Berger, G. Mul, F. Kapteijn, J.A. Moulijn, Six-flow reactor technology a review on fast catalyst screening and kinetic studies, *Catal. Today* 60 (2000) 93–109, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-5861\(00\)00321-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-5861(00)00321-7).
- [8] S.B. Rasmussen, S. Perez-Ferreras, M.A. Bañares, P. Bazin, M. Daturi, Does pelletizing catalysts influence the efficiency number of activity measurements? Spectrochemical engineering considerations for an accurate operando study, *ACS Catal.* 3 (2013) 86–94, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cs300687v>.
- [9] T. Tatsumi, K.A. Koyano, Y. Tanaka, S. Nakata, Mechanical stability of mesoporous materials, MCM-48 and MCM-41, *J. Porous Mater.* 6 (1999) 13–17, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009682915127>.
- [10] A. Galarneau, D. Desplandier-Giscard, F. Di Renzo, F. Fajula, Thermal and mechanical stability of micelle-templated silica supports for catalysis, *Catal. Today* 68 (2001) 191–200, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-5861\(01\)00300-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-5861(01)00300-5).
- [11] K. Cassiers, T. Linssen, M. Mathieu, M. Benjelloun, K. Schrijnemakers, P. Van Der Voort, P. Cool, E.F. Vansant, A detailed study of thermal, hydrothermal, and mechanical stabilities of a wide range of surfactant assembled mesoporous silicas, *Chem. Mater.* 14 (2002) 2317–2324, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm0112892>.
- [12] M. Broyer, S. Valange, J.P. Bellat, O. Bertrand, G. Weber, Z. Gabelica, Influence of aging, thermal, hydrothermal, and mechanical treatments on the porosity of MCM-41 mesoporous silica, *Langmuir* 18 (2002) 5083–5091, <https://doi.org/10.1021/la0118255>.
- [13] P. Van Der Voort, P.I. Ravikovitch, K.P. De Jong, M. Benjelloun, E. Van Bavel, A. H. Janssen, A. V Neimark, B.M. Weckhuysen, E.F. Vansant, A new templated ordered structure with combined micro- and mesopores and internal silica nanocapsules, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 106 (2002) 5873–5877, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp025642i>.
- [14] M. Hartmann, A. Vinu, Mechanical stability and porosity analysis of large-pore SBA-15 mesoporous molecular sieves by mercury porosimetry and organics adsorption, *Langmuir* 18 (2002) 8010–8016, <https://doi.org/10.1021/la025782j>.
- [15] S. Chytil, L. Haugland, E.A. Blekkan, On the mechanical stability of mesoporous silica SBA-15, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 111 (2008) 134–142, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2007.07.020>.
- [16] A. Vinu, V. Murugesan, M. Hartmann, Pore size engineering and mechanical stability of the cubic mesoporous molecular sieve SBA-1, *Chem. Mater.* 15 (2003) 1385–1393, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm0213523>.
- [17] R.A. Mayanovic, H. Yan, A.D. Brandt, Z. Wang, M. Mandal, K. Landskron, W. A. Bassett, Mechanical and hydrothermal stability of mesoporous materials at extreme conditions, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 195 (2014) 161–166, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2014.04.027>.
- [18] L.M. Henning, J.T. Müller, G.J. Smales, B.R. Pauw, J. Schmidt, M.F. Bekheet, A. Gurlo, U. Simon, Hierarchically porous and mechanically stable monoliths from ordered mesoporous silica and their water filtration potential, *Nanoscale Adv.* 4 (2022) 3892–3908, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2na00368f>.
- [19] B. Reid, I. Mane, F. Ahmed, M.J. Fornerod, M. Füreidi, B. Schmidt-Hansberg, A. Alvarez-Fernandez, S. Guldin, Enhanced mechanical stability and scratch resistance of mesoporous aluminosilicate thin films, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 345 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2022.112246>.
- [20] Y. Liu, T.J. Pinnavaia, Mesocellular aluminosilicate foams (MSU-S/F) and large pore hexagonal mesostructures (MSU-S/H) assembled from zeolite seeds: hydrothermal stability and properties as cumene cracking catalysts, *Stud. Surf. Sci. Catal.* 142 (2002) 1075–1082, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2991\(02\)80265-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2991(02)80265-8).
- [21] P. Schmidt-Winkel, W.W.L. Jr., D. Zhao, P. Yang, B.F. Chmelka, G.D. Stucky, Mesocellular siliceous foams with uniformly sized cells and windows, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 121 (1999) 254–255, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja983218i>.
- [22] P. Schmidt-Winkel, W.W.L. Jr., P. Yang, D.I. Margolese, J.S. Lettow, J.Y. Ying, G. D. Stucky, Microemulsion templating of siliceous mesostructured cellular foams with well-defined ultralarge mesopores, *Chem. Mater.* 12 (2000) 686–696, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm991097v>.

- [23] V. Zarubina, H. Talebi, C. Nederlof, F. Kapteijn, M. Makkee, I. Melián-Cabrera, On the stability of conventional and nano-structured carbon-based catalysts in the oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene under industrially relevant conditions, *Carbon* 77 (2014) 329–340, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2014.05.036>.
- [24] C. Nederlof, V. Zarubina, I. V. Melián-Cabrera, E.H.J. Heeres, F. Kapteijn, M. Makkee, Application of staged O₂ feeding in the oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene to styrene over Al₂O₃ and P₂O₅/SiO₂ catalysts, *Appl. Catal. Gen.* 476 (2014) 204–214, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcata.2014.03.002>.
- [25] V. Zarubina, H. Talebi, H. Jansma, K. Góra-Marek, C. Nederlof, F. Kapteijn, M. Makkee, I. Melián-Cabrera, On the thermal stabilization of carbon-supported SiO₂ catalysts by phosphorus: evaluation in the oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene to styrene and a comparison with relevant catalysts, *Appl. Catal. Gen.* 514 (2016) 173–181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcata.2016.01.024>.
- [26] I. Melián-Cabrera, V. Zarubina, C. Nederlof, F. Kapteijn, M. Makkee, An in situ reactivation study reveals the supreme stability of γ -alumina for the oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene to styrene, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 8 (2018) 3733–3736, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8cy00748a>.
- [27] I. Melián-Cabrera, V. Zarubina, Selectivity-induced conversion model explaining the coke-catalysed O₂-mediated styrene synthesis over wide-pore aluminas, *Mol. Catal.* 524 (2022) 112301, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcat.2022.112301>.
- [28] J.J. Mercadal, D. Osadchii, V. Zarubina, M.J. Valero-Romero, I. Melián-Cabrera, Organocatalyst reactivation with improved performance in O₂-mediated styrene synthesis, *Mol. Catal.* 529 (2022) 112525, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcat.2022.112525>.
- [29] J.J. Mercadal, A. Mayoral, J.L.G. Fierro, E. García-Bordejé, I. Melián-Cabrera, Improved O₂-assisted styrene synthesis by double-function purification of SWCNT catalyst, *Chem. Eng. J.* 455 (2023) 140723, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.140723>.
- [30] V. Zarubina, J.J. Mercadal, H. Jansma, I. Melián-Cabrera, Unpredicted porosity improvement upon thermal reactivation of a fouled multi-walled carbon nanotube, *Mater. Lett.* 364 (2024) 136386, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2024.136386>.
- [31] I. Melián-Cabrera, V. Zarubina, H. Jansma, Unravelling a complex catalyst deactivation in which selectivity affects conversion: oxygen-assisted styrene synthesis at industrially-relevant conditions, *Chem. Eng. J.* 494 (2024) 152348, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2024.152348>.
- [32] M.J. Ortiz-Iniesta, I. Melián-Cabrera, Fenton chemistry-based detemplation of an industrially relevant microcrystalline beta zeolite. Optimization and scaling-up studies, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 206 (2015) 58–66, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2014.12.019>.
- [33] M. Thommes, K. Kaneko, A. V. Neimark, J.P. Olivier, F. Rodriguez-Reinoso, J. Rouquerol, K.S.W. Sing, Physisorption of gases, with special reference to the evaluation of surface area and pore size distribution (IUPAC Technical Report), *Pure Appl. Chem.* 87 (2015) 1051–1069, <https://doi.org/10.1515/pac-2014-1117>.
- [34] L.L. Pérez, V. Zarubina, H.J. Heeres, I. Melián-Cabrera, Condensation-enhanced self-assembly as a route to high surface area α -aluminas, *Chem. Mater.* 25 (2013) 3971–3978, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm401443b>.
- [35] S. Lowell, J.E. Shields, M.A. Thomas, M. Thommes, *Characterization of Porous Solids and Powders: Surface Area, Pore Size and Density*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 2004.
- [36] Z. Zhang, J. Yin, H.J. Heeres, I. Melián-Cabrera, Thermal detemplation of SBA-15 mesophases. Effect of the activation protocol on the framework contraction, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 176 (2013) 103–111, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2013.03.048>.
- [37] B.R. Pauw, A.J. Smith, T. Snow, N.J. Terrill, A.F. Thünemann, The modular small-angle X-ray scattering data correction sequence, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 50 (2017) 1800–1811, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600576717015096>.
- [38] J. Filik, A.W. Ashton, P.C.Y. Chang, P.A. Chater, S.J. Day, M. Drakopoulos, M. W. Gerring, M.L. Hart, O. V. Magdysyuk, S. Michalik, M.T. Wharmby, H. Wilhelm, Processing two-dimensional X-ray diffraction and small-angle scattering data in DAWN 2, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 50 (2017) 959–966, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600576717004708>.
- [39] McSAS3: A refactored McSAS for analysis of X-ray and Neutron scattering data. URL: <https://github.com/BAMresearch/McSAS3>.
- [40] L.M. Henning, G.J. Smales, M.G. Colmenares, M.F. Bekheet, U. Simon, A. Gurlo, Synthesis and properties of COK-12 large-pore mesocellular silica foam, *Nano Sel* 4 (2023) 202–212, <https://doi.org/10.1002/nano.202200223>.
- [41] L. López-Pérez, V. Zarubina, I. Melián-Cabrera, The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller model on aluminosilicate mesoporous materials. How far is it from the true surface area? *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 319 (2021) 111065, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2021.111065>.
- [42] I. Melián-Cabrera, V. Zarubina, Surface area per volumetric loading and its practical significance, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 354 (2023) 112549, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2023.112549>.
- [43] S.A. Bagshaw, E. Prouzet, T.J. Pinnavaia, Templating of mesoporous molecular sieves by nonionic polyethylene oxide surfactants, *Science* 269 (1995) 1242–1244, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.269.5228.1242>.
- [44] S.-S. Kim, T.R. Pauly, T.J. Pinnavaia, Non-ionic surfactant assembly of ordered, very large pore molecular sieve silicas from water soluble silicates, *Chem. Commun.* (2000) 1661–1662, <https://doi.org/10.1039/b002856h>.
- [45] L.L. Pérez, S. Perdriau, G. ten Brink, B.J. Kooi, H.J. Heeres, I. Melián-Cabrera, Stabilization of self-assembled alumina mesophases, *Chem. Mater.* 25 (2013) 848–855, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm303174r>.
- [46] J.C. Groen, L.A.A. Peffer, J. Pérez-Ramírez, Pore size determination in modified micro- and mesoporous materials. Pitfalls and limitations in gas adsorption data analysis, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 60 (2003) 1–17, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1387-1811\(03\)00339-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1387-1811(03)00339-1).
- [47] I. Melián-Cabrera, S. Espinosa, J.C. Groen, B. v/d Linden, F. Kapteijn, J.A. Moulijn, Utilizing full-exchange capacity of zeolites by alkaline leaching: preparation of Fe-ZSM5 and application in N₂O decomposition, *J. Catal.* 238 (2006) 250–259, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcat.2005.11.034>.
- [48] R. Strey, W. Jahn, G. Porte, P. Bassereau, Freeze fracture electron microscopy of dilute lamellar and anomalous isotropic (L₃) phases, *Langmuir* 6 (1990) 1635–1639, <https://doi.org/10.1021/la00101a003>.
- [49] L.L. Pérez, M.J. Ortiz-Iniesta, Z. Zhang, I. Agirrezabal-Telleria, M. Santes, H. J. Heeres, I. Melián-Cabrera, Detemplation of soft mesoporous silica nanoparticles with structural preservation, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 1 (2013) 4747–4753, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3ta01240a>.
- [50] V. Zarubina, I. Melián-Cabrera, On the geometric trajectories of pores during the thermal sintering of relevant catalyst supports, *Scripta Mater.* 194 (2021) 113679, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2020.113679>.
- [51] I. Melián-Cabrera, J.J. Mercadal, A. Mayoral, J.L.G. Fierro, On the surface area per volumetric loading: its pronounced improvement in densely-packed SWCNT by double-function purification, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 366 (2024) 112940, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2023.112940>.